
CASE COMMENTARY ON

M.C. MEHTA V. UNION OF INDIA (1988)

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Citation: AIR 1988 SC 1037; (1987) 4 SCC 463.

Judgment: Venkataramiah, E.S. (J)

Petitioner: M.C. Mehta

Respondent: Union of India and Ors.

I. INTRODUCTION

“Environment is defined as the total planetary inheritance and the totality of all resources.” The environment helps humans in development and various other aspects but not vice versa. The environment gets degraded due to the activities of humans that cause harm to the environment. The pollutants from this trade contain “putrescible organic and harmful inorganic material” once discharged in the water, which can wipe out the dissolved oxygen. The outspoken person MC Mehta filed many cases for the protection of the environment. Many industries in present times discharge a large amount of effluents into the water bodies out of which holy Ganga is getting filthy. The pioneer man MC Mehta filed the case in the Supreme Court via a writ petition.

This case is also known as the Ganga pollution case or Kanpur leather tanneries case.

II. FACTS OF THE CASE

- In the pilgrimage city of Haridwar, a smoker tossed a matchstick in the Ganga River in India which caused the river to catch fire for about 30 mins. The river contained a toxic layer of effluents from pharmaceutical firms functioning in that area.
- After this occurrence, M.C. Mehta an environmental lawyer and social activist filed a public interest litigation (PIL) in the Supreme Court of India. This PIL included 89

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respondents in which Respondent 1, Respondent 7, Respondent 8 and Respondent 9 were from the Union of India in 1985.

- Mehta contended in his petition that despite developments in environmental laws, the government authorities had not taken any steps that would be effective in preventing the environmental pollution in the Ganga River.
- The Ganga River was at a vast scale which was a 2500 km stretch and it was impossible to cope with so the court requested Mehta to narrow down the scope and he chose the city of Kanpur, despite being from the city or living there.
- Using the advantage of judicial remedy of the writ, Mehta referred the state agencies to stop the leather tanneries and municipal corporations of Kanpur from taking industrial or domestic pollution and discharging them into the river.
- Few law reports referred to this case as the "Ganga Pollution Case."
- Mehta's petition appealed to the Supreme Court of India to obstruct the respondent in discharging the cathartic pollutants into the Ganga River until they implant some treatment plants to address pollution, especially cyanogenic pollutants to prevent pollution.
- Mehta also requested the court to order the leather tanneries in the Kanpur district to stop releasing untreated effluents into the river and claimed that the Municipal Corporation of Kanpur was not treating domestic biodegradable pollution.

III. ISSUES RAISED

- Whether the authorities recognised the intensifying situation of the sacred water house and investigated the matter?
- Had any measures been taken by the state?
- Do the smaller industries be funded for fixing waste treatment plants?

IV. LAWS AND PROVISION

- Article 21 of the Indian Constitution
- Article 51A(g) of Indian Constitution
- Article 48A of the Indian Constitution

- Article 252(1) of the Indian Constitution
- Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act 1974

V. JUDGMENT

- The court focused on the significance of preventing environmental pollution and also highlighted and by mentioning articles 48-A and 51-A.
- The court recognised the momentousness of the Water Prevention and Control of Pollution Act, of 1974. This act's goal is to forestall and manage pollution and maintain water quality.
- The courts ordered the tanneries to establish primary or secondary treatment plants whichever is possible and convenient.
- The central government was governed by the court to make environmental education mandatory in all educational institutions and free textbooks to be provided and these teachers should be provided training.
- The court criticized the State Board for not taking effective steps to prevent effluent discharge into the Ganga River and the Central Government for not addressing the public nuisance caused by the tanneries.

VI. ANALYSES

In this present case, the question arises of the protection of the environment and prevention of environmental pollution. In this case, the main issue was to preserve the Ganga River from the effluents released in it by various industries leaving the Ganga River polluted. To stop this no one nor the authorities or the individuals who were complicatedly connected to the river laid low with all this. Later the pollution levels of the Ganga River kept on increasing after which necessary steps were needed to be taken. Many tanneries were working in the city of Kanpur functioning and releasing a lot of effluents into the Ganga River making it polluted. So later the Supreme Court of India decided to take measures to reduce the pollution in the Ganga River. The court directed the tanneries to implement some waste treatment plants in their industries to make the discharge less polluted and harmful.

VII. CONCLUSION

The entire case was based on trade effluent which was discharged in the river. These discharges contained toxic pollutants which affected nature badly. This is a remarkable case that shows the importance of protecting and maintaining the natural balance of nature.

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Organisation Conference 1972 was mentioned in the present case. The court mandated the industries to install primary treatment plants. The court also directed the authorities to take various measures in the protection of the river. The obligation is not only on the state but also on the citizens. The citizens can claim fundamental rights but they must perform fundamental duties and protect nature. The harmonious coordination between citizens and the state can raise awareness and development to protect the environment.

REFERENCES

- <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/59060/>
- <https://leap.unep.org/en/countries/in/national-case-law/mc-mehta-petitioner-v-union-india-and-others-respondents>
- <https://indianlawportal.co.in/case-analysis-m-c-mehta-v-union-of-india/>

